

THE APPLICATION OF MEDIUM TEMPERATURE CURED WITH HIGH GLASS TRANSITION TEMPERATURE RESIN SYSTEM ON BICYCLE RIMS

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Abstract

In the past few decades, some bicycle rim manufactures have been using new materials, such as composites, to produce the more reliable but lighter weight products. However, the biggest problem of the use of fibre reinforced polymer composites is the heat resistance during braking the rims because of the heat generation. The generated heat might distort the rims and might cause riding risk but this is not an issue for metals. Thus, in order to obtain higher heat resistance, high glass transition temperature composite materials are adopted and which, in general, means higher temperature (180°C) with longer time in process will be needed. However, this is not very cost effective especially for high cyclic bike industry. Thus, the lower curing temperature, which is about 150°C, and short moulding time, which is about 30 minutes, thermoset matrices are needed due to the convenience of processing. In this study, a medium temperature cure with shortened curing cycle epoxy system, EPO-HTGTM G351N, was taken to discuss on the mechanical properties at room and hot environment to evaluate the performance of materials under the two ambient conditions. It is an IPN structure toughened epoxy system with Tg can be developed up to 180°C. Other two equivalent commercialised systems which have been used to make bike rims currently were compared to explore if the Tg was the only index of materials perform at elevated temperature. Results show that the cured morphology of the selected matrix plays an important role on failure behaviour except Tg.

1 General Introduction

From the beginning of the bicycle era, bicycle rims have always been one of the most talked-about

bicycle components. Bicycle rims have been made of metal, most commonly, steel or aluminium. However, in the past few decades, some bicycle rim manufacturers have begun to produce bicycle rims from other materials, such as composite materials. [1,2] Unlike alloy rims, carbon rims have always had one major hurdle to overcome: heat. Glass transition temperature (Tg) is the temperature at which the epoxy begins to deteriorate. In the case of bicycle rim, when the epoxy reaches Tg the outward pressure of the tire and tube can cause the rim's sidewall to deform, potentially resulting in a catastrophic failure. As with all carbon rims, the heat generated while braking during long and steep descents has always been a challenge for designing the rims. On a long descent, braking temperatures can reach 300°F, resins not designed for high heat will reach their Tg point well below that, resulting in rim failure. Some of the manufactures are using resins heat cured at temperature of 350°F with high glass transition temperature [1]. However, these kinds of resins are not welcome for current bicycle rim manufacturers because of the high curing temperature and long curing cycle. Lower curing temperature and short moulding time are what they need. Another option to consider would be the carbon composite/alloy co-molded rims that are available, but with a slight weight penalty. Besides, higher cross-linked structure for higher Tg may cause materials being brittle and may increase the risk of fatigue and impact. Traditional toughened methods might lower the developed heat resistance. Ways to get optimum between toughness and modulus maintenance should be taken into account.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

Three types of samples were prepared. One is the unidirectional prepreg using TC12K 35 (Tairyfil, Formosa Plastics Corporation) carbon fibres impregnated with EPO-HTGTM G351N epoxy resin (Epotech Composite Corporation). The other two are unidirectional prepregs consisting of the same carbon fibres but different epoxy resins from company D and company S individually. Laminates were cured in a square metal mould at 150°C for 30min as the first step to increase the cyclic moulding rate and then post cured at the same temperature for another 60min for cured structure consolidating. Curing pressures were adjusted to control the resin flow to obtain the desire resin content.

2.2 Test methods

2.2.1 Thermal analysis

Glass transition temperature (T_g) of the cured specimens were determined by Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA, 01dB-Mettravib) according to ASTM D7028. Temperature was swept from 20 to 250°C with a heating rate of 5°C/min.

2.2.2 Flexural and short-beam strength tests

The transverse flexural tests were conducted following the standard of ASTM D-790-03 under a three-point bend configuration in order to understand the performance of selected matrices cooperated with carbon fibres in room and high temperature environments. Tests were run under displacement control mode at a crosshead speed of 6.3mm/min. The span length-to-specimen thickness ratio was 4:1 and the speed of testing of crosshead movement was 1.0 mm/min. The short-beam strength of each sample was tested as demonstrated in ASTM D 2344 and was to evaluate the interlaminar shear strength at the two tested temperature.

2.2.3 Interlaminar fracture toughness test

Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness was measured by the double cantilever beam (DCB) test to estimate the performance of materials on crack resistance. A thin PTFE film, about 12.5 μ , was placed in the mid-plane to be a crack starter. A displacement rate of 1.0mm/min was used to load the specimen in open mode until the crack propagated.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Glass transition temperature

The glass transition temperature of medium temperature cure resin systems are summarized in Table 1. As demonstrating in the table, EPO-HTGTM G351N and resin D both have about 180°C glass transition temperature. Resin S shows higher T_g than other two types, which is about 210°C. Figure 1 illustrates the modulus drop of carbon fibre composites cured with three types of resin systems with increasing temperature. The results show that resin S is supposed to have a higher cross-linked structure.

3.2 Flexural properties

Figure 2 and Figure 3 show the transverse flexural strength and the breaking strain of the laminates cured with three types of medium temperature cured matrices in two ambient conditions. It is believed that resin systems are all designed to have a higher crosslink structure in order to have high glass transition temperature. When a resin is increased the crosslink density, it becomes brittle and leads to lower the breaking elongation [3]. In composites, it is obvious in transverse direction. From Figure 1, as the T_g is up to 210°C, it is reasonable that resin S has a higher crosslink density and that can develop very solid structure with high static mechanical strength. The brittle behaviour is much more apparent for resin D because it has the lowest transverse strength and the lowest breaking elongation as shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3. This might be owing to the cured structure from a poor formula design although its composite modulus maintenance at high temperature is acceptable as

illustrated in Figure 1. EPO-HTGTM G351N resin performed well due to its interpenetrating polymer network that can not only provides cured structure a rigid modulus but also a ductile braking elongation so that a toughened system with higher strength and better elongation is obtained and will be able to increase the reliability of rims performing at room temperature [4].

In the high temperature condition, Resin S is expected to have the best value of transverse strength compared to the other two systems because of it higher T_g; however, the figure shows that the transverse strength at 150°C of laminate cured with EPO-HTGTM G351N, which the T_g from DMA is about 180°C, is slightly higher than the specimen cured with Resin S. This is believed from the effort of IPN structure of cured EPO-HTGTM G351N. By contrast, Resin D displays the worse result due to its poor cured structure as it appears at room temperature.

3.3 Short-beam strength

Short -beam strength were measured according to ASTM 2344 under a three-point bend configuration by shear mode. One of the common failures in composite materials is delamination and which is related to the shear properties of a laminate. The shear failure of laminates is generally dominated by matrix. Figure 4 shows the short-beam strength of the laminates cured with three types of resin systems in the room and hot environment respectively. Specimens cured with EPO-HTGTM G351N resin has shear strength 10% more than other two types because of its IPN structure and the same result can be seen from the test at high temperature though theoretically highly crosslinked structure may have higher thermal properties. Combining this with the observation of transverse flexural strength, it can be concluded that the glass transition temperature is not the only index to determine if a fibre composite can perform well in hot environment but cured structure as well.

3.4 Interlaminar fracture toughness

The interlaminar fracture toughness was measured to evaluate the resistance of fatigue and impact of the three kinds of materials [5]. The tests were undergone at room temperature because materials would be brittle than they were at higher temperature environment in which the modulus drop and the strength would be more concerned. Test results are as demonstrated in Figure 5. Owing to the well toughened structure of the EPO-HTGTM G351N resin, its energy absorption is about 20% more than Resin S and is up to 50% more than Resin D.

4. Conclusion

The rims run, most of the time, at room temperature and under different road conditions such as off-road riding. The fatigue related vibration and the impact related bounce are also the major concerns in addition to the heat generation during braking the wheels. The measurement of material's fracture toughness can be an index to evaluate the reliability. During braking, the modulus maintenance is the first important thing to be considered about in order to avoid the distorted shape and then the second is the strength at the high temperature which is related to whether or not a rim will be fractured catastrophically under this circumstance due to the expanding inner tube [1]. From DMA the tendency of material's modulus varied with a range of temperature can be examined. The off-axial strength and its breaking elongation, here the test was conducted at transverse direction of fibres, at high temperature was adopted to estimate the capability of blast preventing. Laminate cured with EPO-HTGTM G351N resin presents as an optimum material to make bicycle rims although its T_g is not the highest. This indicates that T_g is not the only index to evaluate a material used in rims. Nevertheless, as the most important advantage of carbon fibre composite, the light weight pursuing for bicycle rims keep continuing, thinner walled structure design has been the direction for rim designers. This will be a severe challenge. Higher T_g with better fracture toughness materials are need to increase the reliability. Besides, a reasonable short curing cycle will be always interested by the rim manufacturers for cost efficiency.

Table 1. Glass transition temperature of three type resin systems

	EPO-HTG TM G351N	Resin D	Resin S
Tg (°C)	182	185	213

Figure 1. Longitudinal modulus drop of unidirectional carbon fibre specimens cured with three types of resin systems(S, D and EPO-HTGTM G351N) with increasing temperature.

Figure 2. Transverse strength of unidirectional carbon fibre laminates cured with three types of resin systems- S, D and EPO-HTGTM G351N.

Figure 3. Transverse stress-strain curves of unidirectional carbon fibre laminates cured with resin S, resin D and EPO-HTGTM G351N individually.

Figure 4. Short-beam strength of unidirectional carbon fibre laminates cured with three types resin systems.

Figure 5. Mode I fracture toughness of unidirectional carbon fibre laminates cured with three types resin systems.

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